

A RARE ENCOUNTER OF CIRCUMPORTAL PANCREAS DURING PANCREATICO DUODENECTOMY – A CASE REPORT

AUTHOR'S DETAILS

1. Dr. P.A. Kabilan (*)
Thanjavur Medical College and Hospital
Tamil Nadu Dr. M.G.R. Medical University
Department of Surgical Gastroenterology & GI Oncology
Postal Address: No 129, Indira Gandhi Street, Ariyalur – 621704, Tamil Nadu , India

2. Dr. U. Aravindan
Thanjavur Medical College and Hospital
Tamilnadu Dr.M.G.R. Medical University
Department of Surgical Gastroenterology & GI Oncology

3. Dr. R. Senthil Kumaran
Thanjavur Medical College and Hospital
Tamil Nadu Dr. M.G.R. Medical University
Department of Surgical Gastroenterology & GI Oncology

4. Dr. M. Mathews
Thanjavur Medical College and Hospital
Tamil Nadu Dr. M.G.R. Medical University
Department of Surgical Gastroenterology & GI Oncology

ABSTRACT

Circumportal pancreas (CP) is an uncommon congenital condition occurring approximately in 1.1-2.5% of people, characterized by the unusual fusion of uncinate process of the pancreas to its body, located lateral to junction of the portal vein and superior mesenteric vein (PV-SMV). This case describes a 72-year male patient presented with painless jaundice, itching, and a loss of appetite. Investigative procedures revealed a growth near the ampulla, leading to an endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) with stenting. Following the procedure, patient's bilirubin levels improved, and scheduled for a Whipple's pancreatoduodenectomy. During surgery, CP was identified, with the uncinate process encircling the SMV and fusing with the pancreatic body. An accessory left hepatic artery, originating from the left gastric artery, was also identified. Postoperative pancreatic fistula was managed effectively. First documented in 1987, CP is often discovered incidentally and presents unique surgical challenges, particularly regarding pancreatic duct management and related vascular anomalies. Accurate identification of CP is essential to prevent postoperative complications, including pancreatic fistula and incomplete tumor resection in malignant situations. This case emphasizes the importance of preoperative imaging and intraoperative awareness in managing circumportal pancreas.

Keywords: Circumportal pancreas (CP), pancreatic fistula, pancreatic duct, portal vein, superior mesenteric vein.

INTRODUCTION

Circum-portal pancreas (CP) is an uncommon pancreatic variation found in nearly 1.1% to 2.5% of people [1]. This anomaly involves the unusual fusion of the uncinate process of the pancreas to its body, occurring left of PV-SMV junction. Sugiura et al. first described this condition in 1987 [2]. Generally asymptomatic, CP is often discovered incidentally through imaging or during surgery. Early detection of this rare anomaly is crucial for planning potential additional procedures. This report shares our recent experience with a patient diagnosed with circumportal pancreas intraoperatively.

CASE REPORT

A 72 year old male without significant comorbidities, with painless progressive jaundice, itching, and reduced appetite. Clinical examination revealed jaundice and a palpable gallbladder. Blood tests indicated elevated bilirubin (Total Bilirubin 28) and alkaline phosphatase levels. A triple-phase CT scan of the abdomen with pelvis identified a periampullary growth. Patient underwent ERCP stenting due to cholangitis, with follow-up bilirubin levels decreasing to 1.4. He subsequently underwent Whipple's pancreatoduodenectomy.

Intraoperatively, after ruling out disseminated disease, kocherization was performed, and the gastrocolic omentum was divided to access the pancreas. During the procedure, the uncinate process was found to encircle the SMV and fuse with the pancreatic body completely (Fig 1). In figure 1, **White arrow** indicates Circumportal pancreas fusing with body, **Blue arrow** indicates Transected neck of Pancreas and **Blue loop** indicates encircled SMV-PV junction. An accessory left hepatic artery arising from the left gastric artery (Michelis classification - Type 5) was also identified. Pancreatico Duodenectomy was proceeded and the uncinate was divided using monopolar cautery to retrieve the specimen.

Figure 1 shows Uncinate process fusing with the body of the pancreas (White arrow), Transected neck of the pancreas with prolene stitch (Blue arrow), Blue vessel loop depicts SMV-PV.

Figure 2 shows a retrospective review of the Computerized tomography scan confirmed the presence of Circumportal pancreas.

Table 1 shows his Serum Amylase and Bilateral Drain Amylase levels. Postoperative day one showed elevated amylase levels from both drains (R-2634 & L-917), likely due to the cut surface of the circumportal pancreas, which normalized by day three. On postoperative day 10 patient was discharged without complications.

Table I - SERUM AMYLASE AND BILATERAL DRAIN AMYLASE LEVELS

DAY	RIGHT DT	LEFT DT	SERUM
1	2634	917	67
3	199	81	44
5	27	67	35

DISCUSSION

Circumportal pancreas (CP) is a uncommon congenital anomaly characterized by the unusual fusion of the uncinate process of the pancreas to the body of the pancreas on the left of PV-SMV junction, with an incidence in humans ranging from 1.1% to 2.5% [1]. Typically asymptomatic, it is often identified incidentally during radiological evaluations or surgical procedures.

Sugiura et al. first documented this condition in 1987 as a case of "hypertrophic uncinate process of pancreas wrapping around the Superior mesenteric vein and artery." Since then, various case reports have described this condition, using terms such as "portal annular pancreas" and "complete pancreatic encasement of the portal vein" [2]. The anomaly is believed to result from abnormal rotation and high fusion of the ventral and dorsal pancreatic precursors in the seventh week of fetal development.

CLASSIFICATION

Joseph and Karasaki described a classification system based upon the location of fused pancreatic tissue concerning the splenoportal junction (suprasplenic, infrasplenic and mixed) and main pancreatic duct (MPD) course in relation to the portal vein (anteportal, retroportal, or associated with pancreatic divisum) [3-6]. Our patient was classified as having a suprasplenic anteportal type of circumportal pancreas.

SIGNIFICANCE

Circumportal pancreas is associated with higher risk of postoperative pancreatic fistula (POPF) next to pancreatectomies. Inadequate management of the retroportal duct during surgery can lead to leakage of pancreatic enzymes. Better visualization of the course of pancreatic ducts may be achieved through MRCP, where a pancreatic duct ring sign can be diagnostic [7]. In this case, we did not perform preoperative MRCP.

In about 31% of the cases Circumportal pancreas may be associated with variant arterial anatomy including replaced RHA from the SMA and replaced LHA from the left gastric artery. Inadvertently ligating these variants during surgery can lead to serious complications [8-9]. In our patient, an accessory left hepatic artery was noted. Due to its rarity, At times circumportal pancreas may not be identified easily on preoperative imagings, often being misinterpreted as a caudate lobe of liver extension, periportal lymphadenopathy, or a pancreatic tumor encasing the portal vein [10]. If malignant changes occur in main duct IPMN, tumor cells can expand along both anteportal and retroportal ducts, risking incomplete tumor resection. Various techniques have been proposed to prevent POPF from the circumportal pancreas, such as stapling the retroportal portion, extended resection, and cauterization of the retroportal section; however, no standardized method has been established. In our case, we utilized cautery on the retroportal portion [11].

CONCLUSION

Circumportal pancreas is a rare anomaly requiring comprehensive radiological and anatomical knowledge for proper diagnosis. Failing to recognize the MPD course and variant arterial anatomy can lead to significant complications. Although various techniques exist to prevent POPF from circumportal pancreas, further extensive studies are necessary to standardize the most effective methods.

REFERENCE

1. Ishigami K, Tajima T, Nishie A, Asayama Y, Kakihara D, Nakayama T, et al. The prevalence of circumportal pancreas as shown by multidetector-row computed tomography. *Insights Imaging*. 2011;2:409–414.
2. Sugiura Y, Shima S, Yonekawa H, Yoshizumi Y, Ohtsuka H, Ogata T. The hypertrophic uncinate process of the pancreas wrapping the superior mesenteric vein and artery--a case report. *Jpn J Surg*. 1987;17:182–185.
3. Arora A, Velayutham P, Rajesh S, Patidar Y, Mukund A, Bharathy KG. Circumportal pancreas: a clinicoradiological and embryological review. *Surg Radiol Anat*. 2014 May; 36(4):311-9.
4. Joseph P, Raju RS, Vyas FL, et al. Portal annular pancreas. A rare variant and a new classification. *JOP*. 2010; 11: 453– 455.
5. Karasaki H, Mizukami Y, Ishizaki A, et al. Portal annular pancreas, a notable pancreatic malformation: frequency, morphology, and implications for pancreatic surgery. *Surgery*. 2009; 146: 515– 518.
6. Harnoss JM, Harnoss JC, Diener MK, Contin P, Ulrich AB, Büchler MW, Schmitz-Winnenthal FH. Portal annular pancreas: a systematic review of a clinical challenge. *Pancreas*. 2014 Oct;43(7):981-6.
7. Lath CO, Agrawal DS, Timins ME, Wein MM. Portal annular pancreas: the pancreatic duct ring sign on MRCP. *Radiol Case Rep*. 2015 Oct 21;10(4):42-5.
8. Kabir T, Xuan ZTZ, Chung AYP. Circumportal pancreas: A report of two cases. *Ann Hepatobiliary Pancreat Surg*. 2019 Aug;23(3):300-304.
9. Ohtsuka T, Mori Y, Ishigami K, Fujimoto T, Miyasaka Y, Nakata K, et al. Clinical significance of circumportal pancreas, a rare congenital anomaly, in pancreatectomy. *Am J Surg*. 2017;214:267–272.
10. Connelly TM, Sakala M, Tappouni R. Circumportal pancreas: a review of the literature and image findings. *Surg Radiol Anat*. 2015;37:431–437.
11. Pandrowala S, Parray A, Chaudhari V, Shrikhande SV, Bhandare MS. Portal Annular Pancreas (PAP): an Underestimated Devil in Pancreatic Surgery-Systematic Review of Literature and Case Report. *J Gastrointest Surg*. 2021 May;25(5):1332-1339.